

THE HISTORY OF THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE FIRST HEALING CENTERS IN THE FERGANA VALLEY

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the history of the earliest healing centers established in the Fergana Valley, the conditions under which they were founded, and the challenges they faced during their operation. It also analyzes the establishment of these healing centers during the Tsarist government period and their significance for public health.

Keywords: Ok-Sokent, Pedov, I. Bunin, phlebitis, thrombophlebitis, Hazrat Ayub, Turkestanskije Vedomosti, P.P. Sakirich, A.P. Smirnov, N.A. Semashko.

Introduction. Studying the efforts carried out by the healthcare system in the protection and promotion of human health, which is one of the main factors of social life in the Republic of Uzbekistan, is of particular importance. This is especially true for researching the country's resorts and sanatoriums and their history.

Since ancient times, people have used sunlight, air, and water for healing purposes. These remain the primary therapeutic resources in modern resort treatment. The great scholar Abu Ali Ibn Sina also reflected on these issues in his works, particularly in his treatise *The Canon of Medicine*. He paid special attention to healing through sunlight and analyzed in detail the effects of climate on patients. He emphasized that the therapeutic effectiveness of medication depends, to a certain extent, on climate, as well as on the seasons and time of the year [1.3].

Main Part. The period of the Russian Empire is characterized by the emergence of the first resorts, which were referred to as sanitary-hygienic stations [1.5]. By the late 19th century, treatment with medicinal clay had become

widespread. The Fergana Valley, with its beautiful and rich nature, particularly attracted the attention of researchers from the Russian Empire. They studied the characteristics of the region and concluded that it was beneficial for healing, providing recommendations for the construction of medical facilities.

During this period, the sanitary-hygienic stations that were established, like state institutions, primarily served officers of the imperial army, as well as administrative officials and clerks of the Turkestan region. Local nobles and merchants also visited these stations to restore their health. On this basis, climatic sanitary-hygienic stations were established in Chimyon, Khayrobod, and Qoratepa.

After some time, the use of mineral water sources for therapeutic purposes began. In 1877, Dr. D. Mezdrikov, a physician from the Andijan district, examined the Hazrat Ayub springs. From that period onward, the present-day Jalalabad resort became known to the Russian population.

The population of the Fergana Region, which includes the Fergana Valley, also received treatment with medicinal clay in Ok-Sokent by the late 19th century [1.6]. The valley, with its beautiful and rich nature—whose significance has not diminished even today—particularly attracted the attention of the local population. From a climatic perspective, this area underwent considerable scientific examination and was found to be beneficial for healing, with recommendations made for the construction of a hospital.

The first European-style resort for treating illnesses in Central Asia, known as the “new” Magilon, was established in Pedov (Kokand district) in 1881 by the physician I. Bunin, who worked in Andijan. This source was located in the southern part of the Fergana Valley, in the Kuibyshev district, approximately 8–9 km south of the city of Rishton. The road from Rishton to Pedov consisted of unpaved terrain, and these areas were characterized by arid, waterless landscapes [4.28].

The temperature of the water sources in Pedov was 20–20.5°C. The first analysis of this water source was conducted in 1880 by the chemist Teich at the Tashkent Chemical Laboratory [4.30]. Later, in 1927, Professor V.A. Novikov, in

1934 the chemist Ioffe, and in 1935 Okulich-Kazarinov studied the composition of this water source [4.31]. Some differences between their analyses are explained by the fact that the water was collected during different seasons of the year and from various points of the source. The results of these analyses showed that the water was rich in hydrogen sulfide, sulfate-chloride, calcium, sodium, and magnesium.

In 1881, Dr. Bunin organized the treatment of patients at the Pedov resort. Eight houses, a bathhouse, a kitchen, and utility buildings were constructed, and a garden was established. The number of patients visiting this facility was high, and the treatments produced positive results. The proximity of the city of Rishton helped supply the resort with dairy products, meat, vegetables, fruits, and the necessary workforce [4.33].

The resort operated for three years. After Dr. Bunin's death in 1883, the facility ceased its activities. By 1936, none of the buildings constructed by Bunin had survived, and only a few of the 12,000 trees he had planted remained, while the rest had been used as firewood [4.32]. The hydrogen sulfide and mineral water sources in Pedov were used to treat cardiovascular diseases, including cerebral vascular disorders, sclerosis, hypertension, chronic phlebitis, thrombophlebitis, various neurological diseases, diabetes, liver and gallbladder disorders, musculoskeletal diseases, chronic osteitis, bursitis, arthritis, radiculitis, phlebitis, neuritis, chronic colds in women, and skin diseases.

From the 1870s, Russian physicians began paying special attention to studying mineral waters used for therapeutic purposes. In his works, Dr. Kushelevsky provided information about the famous Hazrat Ayub water in Jalalabad, the hydrogen sulfide-alkaline springs in Pedov, and the salt lakes of Akhsikent. One of the newspapers of that period, *Turkestanskije Vedomosti*, published an article by Dr. Shimansky about the Chimyon sanitary station and P.P. Sakirich's Hazrat Ayub mineral spring. Dr. Bunin first visited these sites in 1878, and after observing the therapeutic effects of bathing in these springs on patients, he continued to visit them.

The Akhsikent salt lake is located in the village of Qamishqorgon, Namangan district, Fergana region. The lake was covered with 1–2 vershoks (a unit of length) of salt, which increased to 5 vershoks during the autumn months, and its area exceeded 310 hectares. Archival sources provide detailed information about the Akhsikent lake, noting that it was well-known among the local population and considered therapeutic, believed to cure various ailments. Wooden cabins for patients were built beyond the salt layer along the lake's shore, and the lake itself was divided into two sections for bathing, with separate baths provided for men and women [2.15].

After the outbreak of the First World War, citizens of the Russian Empire were unable to undergo treatment courses in Germany and Austria-Hungary. As a result, the government raised the issue of establishing “healing centers” within the Russian Empire. Accordingly, in 1914, an expedition consisting of two scientists was sent to the Akhsikent Lake in the Fergana region to determine the presence of radium in the air, water, and mud. According to one of the expedition members, A.P. Smirnov, a natural emanator was discovered at Akhsikent Lake. Rare artificial emanators were considered a primary means for treating metabolic disorders and rheumatism (bod). Installing such emanators was very expensive, and only a small circle of wealthy individuals could afford treatment with them. Based on their examination, the expedition members concluded that the site had strong potential to become an important resort area. The presence of chemically rich mud and saline waters, along with nearby drinking water, made the location convenient and beneficial for patients [3.254].

By the beginning of the 20th century, in addition to sanitary-hygienic stations, treatment facilities of a resort type began to emerge. In 1919, according to a decree signed by the former government, all resorts and sanatoria were transferred to the healthcare system and began serving the population.

As a result of the activities carried out by the national healthcare system, the Shahimardon mountain-climatic resort and 34 children's climatic sanatoria were

established; however, after some time, it became clear that many of these facilities were unsuitable. Later, the Uzbekistan State Research Institute for Physiotherapy and Resorts, named after N.A. Semashko, succeeded in identifying new treatment centers in Uzbekistan. As a result, the Chortoq resort, located in the present-day Namangan region, was established, paving the way for the development of other resorts.

In 1932–1933, the Uzbekistan State Research Institute for Physiotherapy and Resorts, named after N.A. Semashko, studied the areas suitable for treatment in Shahimardon, located in the Vadil district of the Fergana region. As a result, the first climatic sanatorium in Uzbekistan for the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis was established in this location [5.70].

In October 1947, the Institute sent researchers—including Prof. V.M. Faibushevich, Prof. R.I. Yevseev, and B.A. Beder, Candidate of Geological and Mineralogical Sciences—to Namangan region to examine the artesian waters in Chortoq. The investigation confirmed the therapeutic properties of Chortoq water, and from 1948, work began on the possibility of establishing a resort there. The Institute conducted studies in Chortoq for three years, ultimately creating the foundation for building a modern treatment resort in Uzbekistan. This resort was officially included in the national list of resorts by the Decree No. 104 of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 17, 1971 [5.33].

The opening and operational procedures of the recreation and rest facilities at the Chortoq resort were carried out in accordance with the regulations established by Decree No. 654 of the Council of Ministers of Uzbekistan, dated September 5, 1973 [5.33]. By its nature, the resort functions as a treatment facility using natural therapeutic resources and as a balneological treatment center based on the natural climatic conditions.

In the Fergana Valley, the Chimeon resort was established in 1947, and in 1951 a 20-bed stationary treatment facility was opened in the settlement of Chimeon. Another reason for its establishment was the favorable natural conditions for

treatment, which did not escape the attention of former Soviet researchers. The Chimeon sanatorium was classified as a first-class mountain-climatic resort, with barracks-style buildings and a small number of cottages serving as accommodations for both rest-seekers and patients [6.4].

The main therapeutic agent of the Chimeon stationary treatment facility was subthermal chloride-sodium water containing 150–240 grams of hydrogen sulfide per liter. The Uzbekistan State Research Institute for Physiotherapy and Resorts, named after N.A. Semashko, conducted clinical studies of this mineral sulfide water and developed methods for treating patients at the facility.

Conclusion. The early therapeutic facilities in Uzbekistan, established gradually during the periods of the Russian Empire and Soviet rule, were slowly organized, with new water sources being explored and developed over time. As a result, the local population gradually lost the ability to use these facilities independently, and they came under state control. The organization of therapeutic centers under state authority limited access for the less affluent segments of the local population, while military personnel, nobility, and merchants gained priority access. This situation was particularly pronounced during the Russian Empire's rule.

In the years following the rise of the Soviet government, local residents were at least partially granted access to these facilities. Despite certain shortcomings, the therapeutic centers established in the Fergana Valley served both the local population and people of European origin over the years.

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